

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

ALTERNATIVE TENDER PROCESS IN THE FIELD OF SPECTRUM MANAGEMENT

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Abstract

Based on analyses of disadvantages of the present tender process in application to spectrum management activities an alternative one, used in building industry and called as lump-sum or fixed-price process, is considered. It consists in issuing a tender not on proposed structure and volume of equipment and related services that are estimated as corresponding to available financial resource that is unknown by bidders, but on system, equipment and services delivery corresponding to an available financial resource that becomes to be known by bidders, but under mandatory compliance with all technical requirements set out in the tender documentation. Some other considerations concerning the issue are also presented.

Keywords: Spectrum management, spectrum monitoring, spectrum monitoring equipment and services, tender process, lump-sum/fixed-price contracts.

1. Introduction

Implementation of an efficient National spectrum management system (NSMS) and particularly its spectrum monitoring network is a very expensive action and, therefore, it is very important to use the available finance resources in the most effective way. According to the existing international practice, this is achieved by holding a tender for procurement of equipment and related services. Due to the great complexity of modern NSMS equipment, in the case of the vast majority of developing countries there can be only international tenders, which introduce additional difficulties in the tender process.

The preparation and conduct of the tender process and the implementation of its results in relation to spectrum monitoring system are detailed in Annex 1 to the Handbook [1] of International Telecommunication Union (ITU). They are fully applicable to NSMS as a whole, especially since the fact that the cost of computerized frequency assignment and licensing system, including monitoring network control subsystem, is usually much cheaper than the spectrum monitoring equipment of any kind. As it is mentioned in ITU Handbook [2], Annex 1 to ITU Handbook [1] provides a discussion of the procurement process for acquiring a spectrum monitoring system, but much of the discussion also applies to acquiring automated spectrum management systems as well. That annex discusses topics to be considered before issuing a tender, including planning a system and developing its specifications. It includes an outline of a representative tender document, and suggests requirements for site surveys, training, maintenance, documentation, and system acceptance – all of which are steps in the process of acquiring automated equipment and software for spectrum management activities.

As far as in the process of the preparation to a tender on spectrum monitoring network it is necessary to

make an initial planning of this network by the NSM Authority itself, the useful information on the subject is contained in ITU-R Report SM.2356 [3] (ITU-R is Radiocommunication Sector of ITU). In addition, Chapters 2 and 3 of this Report contain very useful information on the optimal ratio of fixed and mobile monitoring stations in a monitoring network, the optimal ratio of attended and unattended fixed monitoring stations, the number of transportable monitoring stations, etc.

Useful information on the tender process is also contained in the Guidelines [4] of ITU Telecommunication Development Bureau (BDT) for the preparation of a tender to set up a new or update an existing spectrum monitoring network. These Guidelines provide some additional information concerning the tender process based on experience gained in the framework of practical participation in the preparation and conducting of a number of tenders on NSMS systems in developing countries with different levels of socio-economic development. Therefore, it is hoped that the material presented here and aimed to improve the tender process will be of interest to a wide range of developing countries.

2. Existing tender process and its disadvantages

Let us start with the general approach to the tender process. The usual practice here is that a NSM Authority having a specific budget for a particular project, which it plans to implement in results of a tender, determines the structure and amount of equipment to be purchased, as well as related services. This amount in the opinion of the NSM Authority, meets the project budget. Based on this assumption the NSM Authority issues the tender on supplying such equipment and services. Simultaneously, bidders participating in the tender must specify the prices they ask for the equipment and services. NSM Authorities often ask for proposals

in two separate parts - technical and commercial (financial). In the course of the evaluation of proposals the technical ones are firstly considered to prepare a short list of the bidders whose proposals meet the technical requirements of the tender. Then commercial proposals are considered but only concerning the bidders who were short-listed.

The winner of the tender is determined by the aggregate of technical and commercial proposals. In accordance with the ITU/BDT Guidelines [4], in the course of the evaluation process the technical proposals may take precedence over commercial ones in accordance with the following weighting criteria: 70% for the technical requirements; 30% for the commercial proposals.

It seems that such general tendering procedure is efficient when there are many providers at the international market and the approximate costs of the goods and services requested by the tender are generally well known. Organizers of the tender may well estimate the approximate volume of purchased goods and services, according to the available budget.

With the NSMS equipment and services, the situation is quite opposite - there are only a small number of suppliers at the international market and their prices are not known in advance. This results from the fact that providers of equipment and services for NSMS usually do not give in advance associated costs referring that they significantly depend on many factors related to the volume of the equipment, its structure, transport expenses, the volume of future civil works and a created infrastructure, etc. NSM Authorities usually try to obtain such data in roundabout ways or rely on the previous tendering experience that not always provides reliable results, when the NSM Authority (even using foreign experts) tries to determine structure and volume of the equipment which it can procure in accordance with available financial resources.

Technical parameters of the equipment the world's major suppliers, are aligned, all suppliers declare "compliance with the ITU recommendations." Therefore, it can happen that bidders will present very similar technical proposals that complicate the evaluation process.

The present practice of tendering concerning NSMS does not also lead to saving of financial resources of NSM Authorities. As far as during the tender evaluation commercial proposals are usually scored only by 30%, bidders do not attempt to reduce prices, even in the interests of competition, because generally the price is relatively less effect on the results of the tender. Equipment providers who are planning to take part in the tender by any ways try to learn (and, as a rule, successfully) the budget of the future project to adjust their proposals to this budget. If it happens, that a NSM Authority, due to the lack of information, would overestimate the budget on planned structure and volume of equipment, it will nevertheless spend such overestimated sums because bidders can adjust a total cost to this budget.

As a result, NSM Authority during a tender might receive about the same not only technical but also commercial proposals from all bidders and the process of their evaluation and selection of the winner becomes

very difficult. In view of these difficulties and uncertainties, the existing tender procedure opens up a wide field for possible corruption.

3. Alternative tender process

It seems that more efficient and less costly can be the alternative tendering approach [5]: to issue a tender not on proposed structure and volume of equipment and related services (estimated by NSM Authority as corresponding to available financial resources), but on system, equipment and services delivery corresponding to an available financial resource that becomes to be known by bidders, but under mandatory compliance with all technical requirements set out in the tender documentation.

For this purpose, the NSM Authority in the tender documentation should present the planned network with the indication of the priority of its elements as it usually concerns monitoring stations. The NSM Authority should also clearly indicate the concrete cost of the project which cannot be exceeded in any case, and request bidders to submit proposals on the creation of the maximum number of monitoring stations from the specified list according to indicated priorities under mandatory compliance with all technical requirements set out in the tender documentation.

Under such approach one of the most difficult problems of the tender process in NSMS field – determination of the volume of required equipment and related services that meets available budget - falls on the shoulders of equipment providers. It is hoped that bidders due to competitive reasons will try to present for implementation the greatest possible volume of equipment/services corresponding to accuracy and operational criteria formulated in the tender documentation. From the bidder's proposals it would be easily seen, which provider offers a larger volume of equipment/services under announced project budget and this should greatly simplify the bid evaluation and decision-making process. Moreover, the greater is the budget of the project, i.e. the greater the volume of the requested equipment/services for the project, the greater the likelihood that bidders will offer different amounts of equipment/services and the easier it will be the winner selection process.

If the structure and volume of proposed monitoring stations and services would appear identical in the offers presented by all bidders (but it seems to be hardly probable for projects of considerable sizes), it will be necessary to carry-out bid evaluation in accordance with the usual criteria such as accuracy and operational characteristics of the equipment, conditions of guaranty, maintenance, calibration, repair, training of personal etc.

Such kind of tender procedure is used in building industry and relevant contracts are called as lump-sum or fixed-price ones [6].

For preparation of the abovementioned list of priorities the much approximated prices presented in Table 1 can be used. Let us repeat that these prices are purely approximate and based on expert estimations for about 2018. Left cost figures correspond to the most optimistic price estimations and the right ones - to the most pessimistic price estimations.

The list of equipment that the NSM Authority would like to get in accordance with the declared budget of the project can be presented in two parts. The first one, the basic (mandatory) list, reflects the minimum required amount of equipment and relevant services as approximately determined based on the budget and the most pessimistic estimates of the cost of the equipment and services in accordance with the right

hand figures of Table 1. The second list is the additional one and it provides a variety of equipment and relevant serviced in the order of priority. Additional list is formed according to the same budget, but approximately relating to the most optimistic pricing on all equipment and relevant services in accordance with the left hand figures in Table 1.

Table 1

System and equipment including relevant services	Tentative costs in million US dollars
National spectrum management centre provided by modern software and the equipment for management of the spectrum monitoring network, including a building and communication means	0.7 – 1.5
Fixed monitoring station in the VHF-UHF frequency bands, including a building or shelter (for remote automated station), an infrastructure and corresponding antennas	1 - 2
Mobile or transportable monitoring station in the VHF-UHF frequency bands, including antennas and a vehicle of a Mercedes Sprinter type for a mobile station	0.7 - 1.5
Set of portable monitoring equipment in the VHF-UHF-SHF frequency bands for VHF-UHF mobile monitoring station	0.5 – 1.3
Fixed monitoring station in LF-HF frequency bands, including a building or shelter, an infrastructure, and single station location (SSL) antenna	0.7 – 1.5
Additional LF-HF equipment for a mobile monitoring station in the VHF-UHF frequency bands	0.5 – 1.0
Mobile monitoring station in LF-UHF frequency band	1.2 – 2.5
Station for satellite monitoring, including a building, an infrastructure and antennas for monitoring of radiocommunication satellites at the geostationary orbit	5 - 10

NSM authority should announce in the tender documents the exact budget of the tender and clearly indicate that a significant advantages will obtain the bidder who offers (in addition to the mandatory equipment of the main list) the largest amount of equipment from the additional list, taking into account the priorities indicated in this list, within a specified budget that may not be exceeded in any case. Upon that, all equipment and services (in both main and additional lists) should certainly meet all the technical, organizational, etc. specifications of the tender.

The procedure can be clarified by the following example. Let us suppose that a NSM Authority of one country has a budget of 15 million US dollars for the project and wants, as a minimum, to update the NSMS equipment in the state capital (city A), and, as a maximum, additionally provide a transportable monitoring station in city A, to equip another big city B and, if it

appears possible, to provide some monitoring equipment for the third city C.

Based on the budget of 15 million US dollars and the pessimistic assessment of the costs of the equipment from Table 1, it is possible to formulate a main (mandatory) list of the equipment, represented at the top of Table 2 for the city A. On the basis of the same budget and the optimistic estimation of all prices from Table 1 it can be possible to create a list of additional equipment for the cities A, B and C as shown at the bottom of Table 2 with indication of related priorities.

In the case when proposals of all bidders meet technical requirements of the tender (on equipment and services) the winner of the tender can be the bidder which is ready to provide the greater number of equipment from the additional list in Table 2 for those 15 million US dollars of the whole project taking into account indicated priorities.

Table 2

Main (mandatory) list of equipment with relevant services			
Name of equipment		Number	City
National spectrum management centre		1	A
Fixed monitoring station in the VHF-UHF frequency bands		3	A
Mobile monitoring station in the VHF-UHF frequency bands		1	A
Mobile monitoring station in the LF-UHF frequency bands		1	A
Set of portable monitoring equipment in the VHF-UHF-SHF frequency bands		2	A
Fixed monitoring station in LF-HF frequency bands		1	A
Additional list of equipment with relevant services			
Priority	Name of equipment	Number	City
1	Transportable monitoring station in the VHF-UHF frequency bands	1	A
2	Fixed monitoring station in the VHF-UHF frequency bands	2	B
3	Mobile monitoring station in the LF-UHF frequency bands	1	B
4	Set of portable monitoring equipment in the VHF-UHF-SHF frequency bands	1	B
5	Mobile monitoring station in the VHF-UHF frequency bands	1	B
6	Set of portable monitoring equipment in the VHF-UHF-SHF frequency bands	1	B
7	Fixed monitoring station in the VHF-UHF frequency bands	1	B
8	Mobile monitoring station in the LF-UHF frequency bands	1	C
9	Set of portable monitoring equipment in the VHF-UHF-SHF frequency bands	1	C

In order to avoid the danger of underestimating by the NSM Authority of its financial capabilities, it can make a postscript to Table 2 along the following lines: "The proposals for additional mobile monitoring stations in the VHF-UHF frequency bands are welcome." It is better to address such a postscript precisely to mobile stations, since in this case the tender will not need to clarify their location and the necessary infrastructure, as is the case in the case of stationary stations.

Other tender considerations should be given in the documentation in accordance with [1] and [4].

If a NSM authority still finds it difficult to divide the equipment and services into mandatory and additional, it can submit a simplified table in the tender, presenting, in the considered case, all the elements of the table in the order of priorities from 1 to 15. Each bidder himself will determine to what extent he can fulfill the priorities of the tender.

If it happens that all bidders submit the same proposals regarding the volume of equipment (which is possible in the case of small tenders), the choice of the best offer can be made on the basis of a comparison of proposals concerning services and other components of the tender in accordance with [1] and [4].

It is obvious that the process of determining the winner of the tender in this alternative procedure is greatly simplified, and the field for possible corruption is significantly narrowed.

4. Other considerations concerning the tender process

It seems appropriate to make a few general comments concerning the tender process, regardless of the scheme of its handling.

The costs mentioned in § 3 above, stipulated by the tender, relate to capital (CAPEX) ones. For the proper implementation of the tender results, operating expenses (OPEX) may also be additionally required, such as salaries and social security of additional personnel, additional costs for renting premises, additional payments for electricity, depreciation charges, fuel payments for vehicles of mobile stations, etc. [7]. These costs should also be taken into account when assessing the total costs (budget) for the project implementation.

All users certainly look for equipment having good technical characteristics. But it is important to avoid overplay. The practice has shown, that the pursuit for increased (and furthermore – for unique) technical characteristics of NSMS and its equipment in the tender documentation do not give any significant advantages in real conditions of developing countries. Quite contrary, it leads to an essential rise in the price of systems and the equipment, also taking into account essential limitation of a free competition and increased requirements for the qualification of operators. Funny cases are also possible when as technical requirements in the tender documentation the best values for one group of parameters of one equipment vendor get out, for another group of parameters - of another vendor, etc. Such approach imposes additional difficulties for providers regarding the preparation of the tender documentation. Moreover, as a result of such approach, it can easily happen that no bidder will be able to meet the entire set of requirements.

Therefore in this case the tender formally should be canceled or it will be necessary to choose the winner of the tender on the basis of any other principles. The last imposes additional loading on the NSM Authority and also creates conditions for submission of legal claims, etc.

Therefore, emphasis on ITU-R documentation and on the certain "average" characteristics which are carried out by all (or at least by the majority) potential bidders, is the optimal approach for developing countries from all points of view. If the bidder declares and confirm the compliance of its equipment to "ITU recommendations" its technical proposals can be considered as to be acceptable. To be sure that it is the fact, NSM Authority in addition to compliance table of equipment parameters in relation to the terms of technical requirements of the tender documentation can ask for additional compliance table of equipment parameters in relation to ITU-R documentation such as Recommendations, Reports and Handbooks on the matter. The bidder should indicate particular item of one or other ITU-R document where each required parameter is reflected.

In accordance with the ITU/BDT Guidelines [4] in the course of evaluation of technical proposals the following weighting criteria can be used:

- 70% for technical requirements; 20% for service requirements; 10% for training.

However, if considered vendors are declaring and proving that their equipment meets ITU recommendations, significantly greater attention should be paid to proposals concerning services and training, for example with the following weighting criteria:

- 50% for technical requirements; 30% for service requirements; 20% for training.

The practice shows that sometimes particularly service and/or training issues become vital for the success of the project. In some cases very expensive equipment, having excellent technical characteristics, cannot be efficiently used due to absence of the necessary maintenance, calibration and repair, and/or unavailability of relevantly trained personnel.

With regard to training, it is necessary to make the following observation. Training of future operators of an equipment, as well as heads of relevant departments (below all of them be called "trainees") are often organized in a country of equipment production in a single session at the time of delivery and/or installation of equipment in a purchasing country before its entry into operation. This practice seems less than effective. Trainees without having any practical work with the future equipment, but often not even having access to it, badly conceive the material, which for them is quite abstract, speculative, separated from the practical life. Presented in these conditions, the material is usually very poorly remembered. Therefore, starting the work with the equipment in the country, trainees have great difficulties with practical use the knowledge that, as it was hoped by trainers, they have received. Assimilation of even the basic functions of the equipment takes a lot of time, a number of complex functions can be not mastered at all.

A more efficient seems to be the training which consists of two sessions with an emphasis on the in-service training. The first relatively short introductory session can be held, as before, at the time of delivery and/or installation of equipment in a purchasing country. During this session trainers present information about the methodology of measurements of emission parameters to be monitored and location procedures, as well as the main characteristics and features of the purchased equipment are overviewed.

With this volume of knowledge, the trainees, under the guidance of trainers from the manufacturer of the equipment in the framework of the in-service training program, start a trial operation of equipment with the aim to master its most frequently performed functions.

After 2 - 3 months, when the trainees become familiar with the equipment and will master its basic functions, a second main training session can be carried-out. During this session in-depth information can be given about all equipment functions and not just in terms of measurement and location procedures, but also in terms of interpreting the measurement and location results, which is no less important. Since trainees are already fairly well acquainted with the equipment and know how to use it, materials, even quite complex, becomes much more understandable and memorable. The total duration of these two sessions, due to their greater efficiency, may be even shorter than the duration of one session under the usual practice.

After such training, the trainees will be much easier to start an independent and full-fledged operation of the equipment. Nevertheless, it would be very useful to provide the constant presence of one or two trainers (depending on the number of equipment) from the equipment manufacturer for a period from several months up to a year, to continue the in-service training program. Experience shows that even after such an in-depth training, trainees in the course of their daily activities are long enough to deal with problems whose solving can only be made with the involvement of the knowledge of such trainers.

5. Conclusion

It seems that advantages of the described lump-sum/fixed-price tendering alternative process in application to spectrum management activities are quite obvious. However, as far as there is no information on

previous practical use it for tendering in the field of spectrum management, the procedure at the moment cannot be specified as a recommended one but it is described here for consideration by a NSM Authorities as the possible option. After accumulation of positive experiences on its successful implementation this alternative tendering procedure in the field of NSMS can be recommended.

References

1. ITU Handbook on Spectrum Monitoring. Geneva, 2011. Annex 1. Monitoring System Planning and Tenders. <https://www.itu.int/pub/R-HDB-23>
2. ITU Handbook on Computer-Aided Techniques for Spectrum Management (CAT), Geneva, 2015. Section 1.4. Steps to acquire automation of spectrum management. <https://www.itu.int/pub/R-HDB-01>
3. Report ITU-R SM.2356. Procedures for Planning and Optimization of Spectrum-Monitoring Networks in the VHF/UHF Frequency Range. Chapter 2. Fundamental decisions by a National spectrum management authority in the course of preparation of the planning process. Chapter 3. Planning and optimization of AOA spectrum monitoring networks. <https://www.itu.int/pub/R-REP-SM.2356>
4. ITU/BDT. Guidelines for countries for the preparation of a tender to set up a new or update an existing spectrum monitoring network. Geneva, 2016. https://www.itu.int/en/ITU-D/Technology/Pages/PUB_BroadcastingSM.aspx
5. A.P. Pavlyuk, S.Yu. Pastukh, A. Yu. Plossky. An approach to development of Guidelines on formulation the technical requirements for spectrum management systems. – Trudi (Proceedings of) NIIR № 2, 2016. Section: Cost characteristics of networks and equipment. (In Russian. See translation into English at the website: <http://www.ircos.ru/en/articles.html>).
6. Joseph Clancey . Lump Sum Contracts: Advantages, Disadvantages & When to Use. <https://www.netsuite.com/portal/resource/articles/accounting/lump-sum-contracts.shtml>
7. Plossky A.Yu. Pavlyuk (Pavliouk) A.P. Approach to cost-modelling for the development of national spectrum monitoring systems. (Published in the same issue of the journal as this article.)